

DATA: _____

FAMILY DEMOGRAPHIC QUESTIONNAIRE

Dear Parents, in the following you can find some questions regarding your family (about you and your son/daughter). We kindly ask you to compile the following questionnaire in every single part. Thank you in advance for your precious collaboration!

1. Name and Surname of your son/daughter: _____

2. Date of birth and

Place: _____

3. Questionnaire filled in by:

Mother Father Both

4. Diabetes onset of your son/daughter: _____

5. Does your son/daughter have the insuline pump?

YES NO

6. Does your son/daughter have the sensor?

YES NO

7. Does your son/daughter have the celiac disease?

YES NO

8. Does your son/daughter have other comorbidities?

YES NO

If yes, what? _____

9. Do the parents live together?

YES

NO

If the parents are separated, the child is in the custody of:

MOTHER

FATHER

BOTH

10. Age of the father: _____

11. Age of the mother: _____

12. Educational level of the father: _____

13. Educational level of the mother: _____

14. Job of the father: _____

15. Job of the mother: _____

16. Other sons/daughters (if yes, specify gender and age): _____

17. In the past, did you have the chance to participate to any initiative involving the Nao/Charlie robot?

Yes once Yes more than once No

18. Within the family, who is the figure of major reference in the diabetes management?

father mother both other.....

19. Besides you, who is in charge of the diabetes management of your son/daughter? (e.g.: grandparents, older siblings ...)

20. Since s/he has diabetes, your son/daughter did participate to one or more daily school trip)?

yes, with a relative yes, without a relative no

21. Since s/he has diabetes, your son/daughter did spend a week or more away from home?

yes, with the family yes with relatives or friends
 yes with organized groups (sport clubs, scouts, etc) no

22. How do you self-evaluate your level of knowledge about a proper diabetes management?

excellent good normal mediocre insufficient

23. How do you evaluate your son/daughter's level of knowledge about a proper diabetes management?

excellent good normal mediocre insufficient

24. How do you evaluate the level of autonomy of your son/daughter with respect to the management of the following aspects of therapy (please put a cross in the corresponding cells):

	s/he's not able	S/he tends to delegate	S/he needs help/supervision	S/he is completely autonomous
Glycaemia monitoring				
Therapy diary compilation				
Insulin doses/bolus evaluation				
Insuline injection				
Carbohydrates counting				
Nutritional diary compilation				
Diabetes kit and corrections preparation and care				

25. How it is the communication between you and your son/daughter about diabetes?

good selective regarding the practical aspects scarce conflictual
 other: _____

26. How would you define your attitude towards the diabetes management of your child?

tends to be overprotective stimulating autonomy both

27. Do you think that your son/daughter is aware of the possible risks caused by a not correct management of the diabetes?

yes no partially

28. After the onset, which kind of aspects related to diabetes did you need to reinforce/deepen?

29. Through which kind of channels did you retrieve these information?

doctor diabetes associations acquaintances with experience in diabetes websites
 blog forum social networks (e.g. facebook) other _____

30. How do you evaluate the level of knowledge on diabetes, socially speaking?

excellent good scarce

Commented [E1]: We mean...among the general public and the society

31. Did you ever meet any obstacles due to diabetes in the following contexts? Please write in the box the level of complexity (from 0-not problematic to 3-very problematic) and give some examples:

school _____

sport _____

social events (birthday parties/sport club events/...) _____

other _____

32. How do you evaluate your confidence level with technology?

excellent good scarce

33. How do you evaluate your son/daughter's confidence level with technology?

excellent good scarce

34. How do you evaluate your knowledge level about mhealth technologies for diabetes? (app, programs,...)

excellent good scarce

35. Did you ever used any technological device to discuss with your son/daughter about diabetes and to monitor him/her?

yes no

if yes, can you please give some examples? _____

36. Did you ever used any technological platform for the daily management of diabetes?

If yes please specify which ones and with which purpose:

37. Do you think it could be useful a tool able to evaluate your knowledge about diabetes mangement through time?

Yes for us as parents yes for our son/daughter yes for both no

DATE: _____

PARENTS INTERMEDIATE QUESTIONNAIRE

Dear parents, hereby you can find some questions regarding your experience with MyPAL app reached in these weeks. We kindly ask you to compile the follow questionnaire in every section. Thank you for your precious collaboration!

NAME AND SURNAME OF YOUR SON: _____

S/HE WAS BORN IN _____

Questionnaire compiled by:

MOTHER FATHER BOTH

1. Please read the following affirmations and, according to your experience, for each one, do choose with a cross your level of agreement on it:

		Totally agree	Partially agree	I don't know	Partially disagree	Completely disagree	Other – Specify what
1	We think that we could continue using MyPAL app every day						
2	We are using MyPal and we think it is complicated						
3	MyPAL app seems to us simply to use						
4	We think that we need the help of an expert technician to use MyPAL app						
5	We are using MyPal app and we think that its several functionality are well integrated among themselves						
6	We think that the functionalities of MyPAL app are weak/superficial						
7	We imagine that the majority of the people could learn to use MyPAL app in few times and without any particular difficulty						
8	We are using MyPal app and we think that its usability is, in general, few handy						
9	We are feeling at ease using MyPAL app						
10	We need more time to be confident with MyPAL app for using it as best we can						

2. Express your opinion on the following aspects of MyPal app, pointing with a cross in the box corresponding to your choice:

MyPAL app	excellent	good	inadequate
Accessibility in general			
Graphic aspect in general			
Usefulness of the proposed glycemic diary			
Completeness of the proposed glycemic diary			
Usefulness of the proposed nutritional diary			
Completeness of the proposed nutritional diary			
Liking the game-quiz			
Usefulness the game-quiz			
Ability to engage your child			

3. In queste settimane, quante volte in media al giorno avete utilizzato MyPAL app?

Less than once at least once 2-3 times more than 3 times other:.....

4. How was happened the access to MyPal app?

	always	often	someti mes	rarely	never
on our son own initiative					
on our own initiative					

5. By whom MyPal app has been used?

	always	often	someti mes	rarely	never
by our son					
by ourside					
all together					

6. Have you found any difficulties in its use?

yes no

7. If yes, can you explain which one? (both yours and your son's)

8. Which kind of functionalities are you appreciating most?

glycemic diary nutritional diary quiz game none

9. For which reason?

10. Is there any aspect of the therapeutic management for which do you think MyPal app is useful, so far?

yes partially no

If yes, which one?

11. Do you think that your son is taking steps in achieving the chosen goals?

yes partially no

12. You have been involved by him in pursuit of the same ones?

yes partially no

If yes, in what way?

13. In what way your child is pursuing its objectives?

14. Do you think he/she could reach them autonomously?

yes maybe no

15. What do you think is most affecting about his motivation?

16. In general, what thing could motivate him/her?

17. Are there any critical issues that you wish to report at this stage, regarding MyPal app in general?

18. Give an opinion on your overall impression of MyPal app accrued up to now:

completely satisfied partially satisfied completely dissatisfied

DATE: _____

PARENTS FINAL QUESTIONNAIRE

Dear parents, hereby you can find some questions regarding your experience with MyPAL app reached in these weeks. We kindly ask you to compile the follow questionnaire in every section. Thank you for your precious collaboration!!

NAME AND SURNAME OF YOUR SON: _____

S/HE WAS BORN IN _____

Questionnaire compiled by:

MOTHER FATHER BOTH

1. Please read the following affirmations and, according to your experience, for each one, do choose with a cross your level of agreement on it:

		Totally agree	Partially agree	I don't know	Partially disagree	Completely disagree	Other – Specify what
1	We think that we could continue using MyPAL app every day						
2	We think that MyPAL is too difficult to use						
3	MyPAL app seems to us simply to use						
4	We think that we need the help of an expert technician to use MyPAL app						
5	We think that the several functionality of MyPAL app are well integrated among themselves						
6	We think that the functionalities of MyPAL app are weak/superficial						
7	We imagine that the majority of the people could learn to use MyPAL app in few times and without any particular difficulty						
8	We think that the usability of MyPAL app is, in general, few handy						
9	We were at ease using MyPAL app						
10	We need more time to be confident with MyPAL app for using it as best we can						
11	It seemed that MyPAL app was easy accessible for us						
12	We think that MyPAL app is pleasant regarding the graphical point of view						
13	We think that MyPAL app is useful in order to manage diabetes every day						
14	We have showed/talked about MyPAL app with other people						
15	Our son have showed/talked about						

	MyAPP app with his/her coetaneous						
16	We would change many aspects of MyPAL app						
17	In these weeks it was difficult for us to have constantly access to MyPAL app						
18	In these weeks our son have asked to us to use MyPAL app on his/her own initiative						
19	MyPAL app was easliy accessible for our son						
20	Our son have enjoyed MyPAL app						
21	We think that MyPAL app have engaged our son more actively in the management of the diabetes						
22	We think that MyPAL app could be a valid support for our son, to facilitate an autonomous management of the diabetes						
23	Our son have asked us to oversee him/her using MyPAL app						
24	We often have enjoyed MyPAL app together with our son						
25	Sometimes MyPAL app was an occation to share with our son the diabetes management, in a different way from the usual one						
26	Our son apperead to us more motivated in using MyPAL app in order to reach his/her objectives						
27	It was difficult for us to integrate the usability of MyPAL app with all the other necessary tasks for the diabetes management every day						
28	MyPAL app doesn't seem to us competitive with te other devices that we already use						
29	MyPAL app would be more useful if it had other features in addition to those present						
30	We would recommend MyPAL app to other families						

Thank you for your collaboration!